

EUROTHERM2023-V141

Experimental evaluation at high temperatures of the corrosive behaviour of PCMs based on inorganic salts

Franklin R. Martínez Alcocer^{1,2}, Emiliano Borri¹, Svetlana Ushak^{2,3}, Cristina Prieto⁴, Luisa F. Cabeza¹

¹ GREiA Research Group, University of Lleida, Pere de Cabrera s/n, 25001-Lleida, Spain, Phone: +34 973 003576, e-mail: luisaf.cabeza@udl.cat

² Center for Advanced Research in Lithium and Industrial Minerals, University of Antofagasta, Avenue Universidad de Antofagasta 02800, Antofagasta, Chile. e-mail: svetlana.ushak@uantof.cl

³ Departamento de Ingeniería Química y Procesos de Minerales University of Antofagasta, Avenue Universidad de Antofagasta 02800, Antofagasta, Chile.

⁴ University of Seville, Department of Energy Engineering, Camino de los Descubrimientos s/n, 41092, Seville, Spain, e-mail: cprieto@us.es

Abstract

Thermal energy storage (TES) is recognized as a key technology for the implementation in CSP plants productive process. Phase change materials are the materials used in latent TES, but they present corrosion to metals which are in contact, especially inorganic salts. In this study, four inorganic PCMs are tested against two stainless-steel fibres, to evaluate the corrosion effect of each PCM. Results show that hydroxide-based PCMs are more corrosive than nitrate-based salts. After one week, stainless-steel fibres, which were immersed in hydroxides, were destroyed and, fibres which were immersed in nitrates salts retained their integrity.

Keywords: Thermal energy storage (TES), corrosion test, inorganic PCMs

1. Introduction

In the last decades, CSP plants improved their technologies incorporating into their production process two molten salt tanks, storing energy in pure sensible way [1], which represents 12% of the installation costs [2]. However, replacing molten salt tanks with a tank composed of PCMs with different melting temperatures (cascade configuration) is more efficient, since latent heat is greater than sensible heat, which means that a greater amount of thermal energy can be stored with a smaller amount of material [1]. Moreover, to implement this technology it is necessary to develop PCMs with melting temperatures in the range of 300°C to 600°C (traditional operating temperature range of CSP plants) [3]. From an application point of view, inorganic salts are considered optimal for this aim, because they have high energy storage density. However, most authors agree that one of the main drawbacks of the use of PCM when high power is needed is the low thermal conductivity of the materials [4]. Furthermore, to overcome these problems, the addition of metal wool to PCM is an attractive option, since metal wools have high thermal conductivity and they are economically cheap. Nevertheless, inorganic salts are corrosive, which represented one of the most relevant phenomena to be considered for designing TES systems [5]. In this study, the corrosion effect of four different inorganic compounds, NaNO₃, KNO₃, NaOH and eutectic mixture NaOH-NaCl (80-20 wt.%) was evaluated, using two commercial stainless-steel fibres as substrate.

2. Materials and methodology

2.1. Materials

In this study, four different PCMs with similar melting temperatures, two nitrates and two hydroxides-based compounds, were selected to carry out this research. Thermal properties and details of the reagents were used to prepare PCMs are summarized in Table 6. Details and properties of selected PCMs [6]

Table 6. Details and properties of selected PCMs [6]

PCM	T _{melting} (°C)	ΔH _{melting} (J/g)	Source	Reference
NaNO ₃	310	172	Sigma-Aldrich	[1]
NaOH	318	165	Sigma-Aldrich	[7]
KNO ₃	335	95	VWR Chemicals	[8]
NaOH-NaCl (80-20 wt.%)	370	370	Sigma-Aldrich – Pan Reac Applichem	[7]

Moreover, two commercial stainless-steel fibres were selected as a substrate. They were stainless steel 314 and 434. Their main characteristics are given in Table 7. Composition of commercial stainless-steel fibres [6]

Table 7. Composition of commercial stainless-steel fibres [6]

Substrate	Fibre 314		Fibre 434	
Chemical composition (%)	C	0.20	C	0.08
	Si	2.50	Si	1.00
	Mn	2.00	Mn	1.00
	P	0.045	P	0.04
	S	0.015	S	0.03
	Cr	24 -26	Cr	16 – 18
	Ni	19 - 22	Mo	0.90 – 1.30

2.2. Methodology

Briefly, four samples (0.30 g approx.) of each stainless-steel fibre were placed in tests tubs. After that, test tubs with the stainless-steel fibre samples were filled with 15 g of four solid PCMs (NaNO₃, KNO₃, NaOH and eutectic mixture NaOH-NaCl (80-20 wt.%)), as it can see in Figure 42. Immersion of stainless fibres in each PCM. Left: solid, right: liquid All the test tubes were placed in the muffle at 450°C (see Figure 42. Immersion of stainless fibres in each PCM. Left: solid, right: liquid, to ensure liquid state of the PCM. The stainless-steel fibres were immersed in liquid PCM for one week. In addition, the corrosion tests were carried out in duplicate.

Figure 42. Immersion of stainless fibres in each PCM. Left: solid, right: liquid

3. Results

From the samples assessed it was possible to observe that both of studied stainless-steel fibres present corrosion at naked eye after immersion into NaNO_3 , NaOH , NaOH-NaCl (80-20 wt.%) and KNO_3 during the entire experimental period (Figure 2). These results are in accordance with the literature [5], where it was previously shown that one of the disadvantages of using inorganic PCM is their high corrosive effect. Furthermore, nitrates showed to be less corrosive than hydroxides, as shown in Figure 2, stainless-steel fibres that were immersed in hydroxides were completely destroyed compared to stainless-steel fibres that were immersed in nitrates, which despite showing corrosion retained their integrity.

Fibre 314				
Before tests	NaNO_3	NaOH	NaOH-NaCl (80-20 wt.%)	KNO_3
Fibre 343				
Before tests	NaNO_3	NaOH	NaOH-NaCl (80-20 wt.%)	KNO_3

Figure 43. Corrosion of stainless-steel fibres in contact with NaNO_3 , NaOH , NaOH-NaCl (80-20 wt.%) and KNO_3

4. Conclusions

Corrosion experiments were carried out amongst two stainless-steel fibres immersed in four different PCMs, two nitrates and two hydroxides. The degradation phenomena were analysed qualitatively after the immersion of stainless-steel fibres in PCMs for one week. Considering the visual changes of the immersed stainless-steel, hydroxides showed to be more corrosive than nitrates.

Acknowledgements

Franklin R. Martinez Alcocer thanks the National Doctorate Scholarship for foreign students ANID 2021 Folio 21211932 for the financial support in the research. This project was funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement 101084182 (HYBRIDplus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This work is partially supported by ICREA under the ICREA Academia programme. The authors would like to thank the Catalan Government for the quality accreditation given to their research group (2021 SGR 01615). GREiA is certified agent TECNIO in the category of technology developers from the Government of Catalonia.

References

- [1] C. Prieto, L.F. Cabeza, Thermal energy storage (TES) with phase change materials (PCM) in solar power plants (CSP). Concept and plant performance, *Appl. Energy*. 254 (2019) 113646. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113646>.
- [2] IRENA (2021), Renewable capacity statistics 2021, Abu Dhabi, 2021.
- [3] B. Banerjee, S. Chatterjee, J. Datta, S.D. Saha, Application of phase changing materials in a CSP plant for thermal energy storage: A review on recent developments, *Mater. Today Proc.* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.04.306>.
- [4] C. Prieto, A. Lopez-Roman, N. Martínez, J.M. Morera, L.F. Cabeza, Improvement of phase change materials (PCM) used for solar process heat applications, *Molecules*. 26 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26051260>.
- [5] P.E. Marín, S. Ushak, A. de Gracia, M. Grageda, L.F. Cabeza, Assessing corrosive behaviour of commercial phase change materials in the 21–25 °C temperature range, *J. Energy Storage*. 32 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2020.101711>.
- [6] STAX metal fibres, (n.d.). <https://www.stax.de/en/> (accessed January 23, 2023).
- [7] M. Liu, W. Saman, F. Bruno, Review on storage materials and thermal performance enhancement techniques for high temperature phase change thermal storage systems, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 16 (2012) 2118–2132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.01.020>.
- [8] H. Michels, R. Pitz-Paal, Cascaded latent heat storage for parabolic trough solar power plants, *Sol. Energy*. 81 (2007) 829–837. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2006.09.008>.